

Densification of pure alpha alumina ceramics with chromia as dopant

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Abstract : Sintering behavior of pure α - Al_2O_3 powder based alumina compacts in presence of *in situ* formed microfine Cr_2O_3 precursor as sintering aid has been investigated. The effect of minor incorporation (1.0 wt%) of *in situ* Cr_2O_3 precursor derived from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ gel on thermal treatment around 500 °C to the pure α - Al_2O_3 powder compacts exhibits profound mineralizing action on the densification of pure α - Al_2O_3 ceramics resulting in excellent thermomechanical properties and coherent corundum body at a relatively low temperature of firing (1550 °C). The high sinterability of α - Al_2O_3 is attributed to formation of isovalent and isostructural solid solution of Cr_2O_3 in Al_2O_3 matrix leading to a non-hazardous, stable alumina ceramics. The *in situ* Cr_2O_3 precursor is observed to function as a normal grain growth accelerator in pure α - Al_2O_3 sintering probably through enhancement of grain boundary mobility to a certain extent.

Keywords : Chromia precursor, alpha-alumina, densification, alumina-chromia solid solution, microstructure.

Introduction

Nowadays high purity sintered Al_2O_3 ceramics ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 > 99.7\%$) draws special attention because of its unique combination of thermomechanical, mechanochemical and refractory properties suited for multifarious industrial applications. A wide spectrum of pure alumina products finds potential applications as refractory, slide gate valves, engine components, computer substrates, grinding media, abrasives, automobile spark plug insulators, hip prosthesis, catalyst carriers and crucibles for melting metals. However, the solid state sintering of pure Al_2O_3 powder in absence of a liquid phase is a difficult task which is largely based on either lattice diffusion or grain boundary diffusion mechanism or both operating simultaneously, thereby necessitating a very high temperature (greater than 1700 °C) for its effective densification. So the recent research towards development of specialty Al_2O_3 ceramics of desired characteristics mainly rests on

(i) proper selection of high purity Al_2O_3 in suitable crystalline variety, fineness of powder in micrometer level and its grain morphology, and

(ii) choice of novel compatible sintering aid to assist lowering of sintering temperature with a controlled microstructure.

In fact, there is immense scope of work on the solid state sintering behavior of pure Al_2O_3 ceramics by incorporation of reactive oxide precursors as dopant without much affecting the grain boundary chemistry of the Al_2O_3 system.

Some of the important literatures on the sintering of pure Al_2O_3 and mullite are reviewed below :

Blackburn and co-workers investigated the mechanism of wetting and adherence of sintered alumina by the metals like nickel, cobalt, iron, chromium with the objective of preparing well-bonded cermets for jet engines. They reported that there is no inherent tendency of the metals to wet alumina below 1650 °C, the only wetting occurs with chromium in the slightly oxidizing atmosphere due to the formation of chromic oxide which readily forms solid solution with alumina. They concluded that wetting and adherence are developed through thermochemical reactions involving glass-free interfacial compounds in which the metal oxide combined with alumina and the consolidation depends on the amount and rate of oxide formed and its rate of reaction with alumina¹.

Effect of Cr_2O_3 on the sinterability and properties of mullite-spinel composites has been reported by Zawrah using different proportions of pre-synthesized mullite and

magnesium aluminate spinel up to 1550 °C and demonstrated that the addition of 2 wt% Cr₂O₃ results in improvement of physical and mechanical properties of mullite-magnesium aluminate bodies during heating at 1550 °C owing to its solid solution both in mullite and spinel phases².

Manor investigated the grain growth inhibition in nanocrystalline Al₂O₃ doped with chromia, which revealed distinct inhibition of grain growth in the presence of dopant. The unique microstructure composed of nanoscale structure having subgrains in 80–100 nm range along with significant increase of micro-hardness was observed³.

The investigation on final stage sintering behavior of ultrahigh pure Al₂O₃ doped with lanthanum and yttrium (1000 ppm) by Fang *et al.* revealed that doping with larger cationic size yttrium and lanthanum decreased the densification rate by segregation at the grain boundary of the Al₂O₃, thereby blocking the diffusion of ion along the grain boundaries and decreasing the grain growth and coarsening rate during sintering⁴.

Sintering study on various Al₂O₃-Cr₂O₃ compacts composed of fine calcined alumina and chromic oxide upto a temperature of 1700 °C focused that densification increases with the increase in sintering time and temperature. However, densification tends to decrease with increase in Cr₂O₃ content, showing a maximum density of 3.452 g/cm³ by 2.0% Cr₂O₃ addition at 1700 °C. The porosity of the compacts, rate constant and activation energy were reported to increase with increase in Cr₂O₃ content, but tensile strengths showing an inverse relationship with the Cr₂O₃ content⁵.

Sarkar *et al.* studied the role of Cr₂O₃ up to 4 wt% on the properties of reaction sintered MgO-Al₂O₃ spinels with varying molar ratios for MgO : Al₂O₃ (2 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2) using single stage sintering technique in the temperature range 1550–1650 °C. Cr₂O₃ was shown to act as an effective additive for grain growth of all the three different spinel compositions at 1650 °C particularly in alumina-rich spinel⁶.

The sintering and mechanical behavior of alumina-spinel refractory bodies through addition of chromia/zirconia and their mixtures highlighted that alumina-spinel composition exhibited the best sintering and mechanical properties. The addition of either chromia or zirconia led to the pronounced improvement in sintering, mechanical and refractory properties, though the addition of chromia/zirconia mixture yielded the best of such properties⁷.

Parya *et al.* studied the role of *in situ* ZnAl₂O₄ spinel precursor as sintering aid for pure alumina system. Enhanced densification of alumina bodies with uniform microstructure occurred through minor addition of *in situ* ZnAl₂O₄ spinel precursor at 1500 °C, where spinel precursor was observed to act as a grain growth inhibitor for pure alumina system⁸.

The minor presence of *in situ* MgCr₂O₄ spinel derived from the co-precipitated hydrogel (1.0% w/w) to alumina exhibited profound mineralizing action on densification of α-Al₂O₃ with the development of excellent mechanical properties and dense microstructure of α-Al₂O₃ spinel composite at the sintering temperature as low as 1550 °C⁹.

In this context, binary phase equilibrium diagram of Al₂O₃-Cr₂O₃ system demonstrated that alumina forms complete solid solution with Cr₂O₃ without any eutectic and the resultant compound is also highly refractory in nature.

Considering all the aspects cited above, the present investigation has been undertaken to study the effect of minor addition of *in situ* formed Cr₂O₃ precursor on the densification and microstructural changes of pure α-Al₂O₃ ceramics in terms of dopant dosages and sintering temperature with the object of generating a tailored super specialty pure alumina ceramic.

Experimental

The starting materials chosen for the study were pure α-Al₂O₃ powder (ALCOA, GmbH, Germany, Al₂O₃ > 99.7%) as matrix and synthetic Cr(OH)₃ gel as dopant. Cr(OH)₃ gel was synthesized from the interaction of 0.2 molar (NH₄)₂Cr₂O₇ (Analytical reagent grade, Merck) in concentrated H₂SO₄ medium preheated at 70 °C followed by addition of methanol. At first, Cr⁶⁺ solution was reduced completely to Cr³⁺ ions by *in situ* formed formaldehyde by methanol-sulphuric acid interaction followed by removal of excess methanol and formaldehyde on boiling. Finally Cr³⁺ ions was precipitated as Cr(OH)₃ by addition of (1 : 1) NH₄OH at pH 8.5. The formed gel was allowed to age for 24 h. It was then filtered under suction, washed with hot water to remove the soluble impurities, dried under vacuum at 70 °C and pulverized. The pulverized gel powder was then characterized by DTA, FTIR, specific surface area, particle size distribution, XRD and SEM studies. Pure Al₂O₃ powder was also tested for average particle size, surface area, crystalline variety and grain morphology. Specific surface area of the dried pre-

cursor and as received alumina powders were determined from low temperature N₂ adsorption data using BET principle. Differential thermal analysis of the sample was carried out by Shimadzu DT-40 thermal analyser, Japan at a heating rate of 10 °C per min.

FTIR spectrogram of chromia precursor was recorded by Perkin-Elmer-783, UK instrument in KBr phase in the wave number range 400–4000 cm⁻¹. Particle size distribution of powders was measured by ZEN-1600 Malvern Zeta Sizer, USA in the range 0.06–6.0 micrometer. Batch compositions data with varying proportions of Cr₂O₃ precursor calcined at 400 °C are given in the Table 1.

Table 1. Batch composition (w/w)

Batch	α-Al ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃ precursor
BO	100	0
CH1	99.5	0.5
CH2	99.0	1.0
CH3	98.5	1.5

Each batch was thoroughly wet mixed with methanol medium in an electrical mixer. Then dried and pulverized batch mixes were then pressed into cylindrical discs (2.0 cm dia × 2.0 cm height) and rectangular bars hydraulically at a pressure of 1500 kg/cm² by adding 2.0% of moisture. Pure alumina compact without any additive was also prepared following the same procedure for comparison. Each sample was dried at 110 °C in an air oven and subjected to firing at temperatures 1450–1550 °C under reducing atmosphere in an electrically operated programmable furnace for 2 h. The degree of densification of fired samples was evaluated by measuring different physical properties such as linear shrinkage on firing, bulk density, apparent porosity and cold crushing strength following standard methods (ASTM C133-94 and C20-00).

The crystalline phase analysis of compacts fired at 1550 °C was performed on the powder samples in a Philips automatic X-ray diffractometer (Pro EXPERT PW-3071) using Ni-filtered Cu-K_α radiation of 1.5405 Å at a scanning rate of 2° min⁻¹. Micro-structural features of freshly fractured surfaces of sintered samples fired at 1550 °C were studied by scanning electron microscopy (QUANTA 200, FEI make, Holland).

Results and discussion

The densification behavior of finer α-Al₂O₃ powder has been studied by adding minor percentages of reactive

Cr₂O₃ precursor (0.5–1.5 w/w%). The physico-chemical characteristics of α-Al₂O₃ powder and dried Cr₂O₃ gel precursor are presented respectively in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. Physico-chemical characteristics of alumina powder

Chemical analysis :	
Constituent	Amount (wt%)
Al ₂ O ₃	99.72
Na ₂ O	0.21
SiO ₂	0.01
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.02
CaO + MgO	0.02
Loss on ignition	0.02
Physical property :	
Texture	Granular, opaque, white
Average particle diameter (µm)	0.98
Specific surface area by BET (m ² /g)	5.8
Particle size distribution (µm)	0.6–1.2
Crystalline variety	α-Al ₂ O ₃

Table 3. Characteristics of Cr₂O₃ precursor powder

Property	
Texture	Soft, fluffy, green
Solid content (wt%)	41.2
Loose bulk density (g/cm ³)	0.21
DTA peak temperatures (°C)	184, 330 (endo), 398.5 (exo)
Specific surface area by BET (m ² /g)	296.4
Average particle diameter (µm)	0.298
FTIR (cm ⁻¹)	3748, 3421, 2361, 1622, 1157, 623, 556
Crystallinity	
(a) as prepared	(a) Amorphous
(b) calcined at 400 °C	(b) Poorly crystalline Cr ₂ O ₃

The typical analysis of alumina powder indicates high purity of the sample with low alkali and trace silica content which are considered as the most detrimental constituents for generation of high purity alumina compacts. The alumina powder also possesses considerably high surface area with narrow microfine particle size distribution. The alumina powder is composed of α-Al₂O₃ as sole crystalline phase.

From Table 3 it is quite evident that synthetic Cr_2O_3 precursor is very soft, fluffy and green in appearance. It is composed of pure, homogeneous, high specific surface area based nano fine particles. The XRD pattern of the prepared chromia precursor dried at 110°C exhibits amorphous character while low intensity peaks are found for heat treated samples at 400°C corresponding to poorly crystalline grimaldite structure (Fig. 1a). Endothermic DTA peak at 184°C is due to dehydration of Cr_2O_3 hydrogel while peak at 330°C is due to the formation of chromium oxy hydrate by partial dehydroxylation of amorphous chromium hydroxide. The main exothermic peak at 398.5°C is attributed to the formation of poorly crystalline Cr_2O_3 precursor. The presence of IR band above 3700 cm^{-1} is attributed to the stretching vibration

of loosely bound water molecules attached to Cr^{3+} ions while broad IR band at 3421 cm^{-1} is assigned to bound water tetrahedrally bonded with Cr^{3+} ions in the molecules. The band at $2341\text{--}2361\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to coupling effect of stretching and bending vibration of OH groups. The band appeared at 1622 cm^{-1} is related to Cr-OH bending vibration of the molecule, while spectra at 1157 cm^{-1} is assigned to the vibration of Cr=O bonds in the molecules. The strong absorption bands at 556 and 628 cm^{-1} is assigned to the presence of six coordinated Cr^{3+} ions in the molecules. All these OH and Cr-O vibrations are the characteristics of Cr-O-OH hydrate (Fig. 1b). SEM micrograph of the calcined chromia precursor at 400°C shows plate like particle morphology with average particle size of $0.298\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 1(a). XRD pattern of chromia precursor calcined at 400°C .

Fig. 1(b). FTIR spectra of chromia precursor.

Microfine *in situ* Cr₂O₃ powder so generated on heat treatment around 400 °C from Cr₂O₃ hydrogel is likely to behave as a effective seeding material for the densification of α-Al₂O₃ system as the ions of Al and Cr are isovalent and isostructural as well as Al₂O₃ and Cr₂O₃ form ready solid solution without formation of any low melting eutectic.

The sintering was carried out in reducing atmosphere in order to avoid oxidation Cr³⁺ to Cr⁶⁺. The fired color of the sintered compacts is ruby-red. The color intensifies with increase of chromia dosages in the batch. In order to judge the doping role of *in situ* formed transition Cr₂O₃ precursor on the sinterability of α-Al₂O₃ compacts, the temperature of firing was restricted to a lower range from 1450–1550 °C. The densification of the compacts is evaluated by the changes in firing shrinkage, apparent porosity, bulk density and cold crushing strength properties of the sintered alumina compacts. The changes of the above properties against firing temperature are graphically shown in Figs. 2–5.

Fig. 2. Variation of firing shrinkage (%) against firing temperature (°C) for alumina compacts.

It is evident from Fig. 2 that with increase of firing temperature, firing shrinkage increases progressively up to maximum temperature of firing for all the batches. However, higher firing shrinkage is noted in samples containing Cr₂O₃ precursor as dopant than that of dopant-free fired compacts. This may be attributed to the enhanced material interaction and material transport by diffusion mechanism with consequent enhanced shrinkage and elimination of porosity. But addition of higher percentage of Cr₂O₃ precursor around 1.5% to alumina com-

Fig. 3. Variation of apparent porosity (%) against firing temperature (°C) for alumina compacts.

Fig. 4. Variation of bulk density (g/cm³) against firing temperature (°C) for alumina compacts.

Fig. 5. Variation of cold crushing strength (kg/cm²) against firing temperature (°C) for alumina compacts.

compact results in reduction of firing shrinkage for α -Al₂O₃ compacts. The maximum firing shrinkage (14.96%) has been observed with 1.0% dopant loading during firing at 1550 °C. The slope of the curve firing shrinkage vs temperature curve depicts a high degree of sintering of alumina up to the maximum temperature of firing. However, in all the dosages of dopant, the overall shrinkage values are within reasonable limit and as such neither cracks nor distortion is detected in the sintered body.

The degree of densification is normally manifested through the magnitude of apparent porosity. From Fig. 3, it is evident that the apparent porosity reduces sharply at 1500 °C in all additions of Cr₂O₃ dopant and falls to below 0.3% only at 1550 °C while dopant-free compacts show 3.45% apparent porosity under the same condition. More or less fully densified Al₂O₃ compacts are derived in presence of only 1.0% *in situ* formed Cr₂O₃ precursor at 1550 °C. But higher percentage of Cr₂O₃ (1.5%) exhibits some what adverse effect on the sintering of α -Al₂O₃ compacts probably due to the non compatible interfacial bonding at the grain boundary. The minute *in situ* formed Cr₂O₃ dopant shows positive mineralizing action towards the development of sintered pure alumina compacts. This is ascertained from the higher apparent porosity results shown by the dopant-free alumina compacts at all firing temperatures.

The variation of bulk density reveals that irrespective of Cr₂O₃ addition, the appreciable improvement of bulk density has been accomplished for α -Al₂O₃ compacts during a given temperature of firing and approaches to a maximum value at 1550 °C. It is interesting to note that the appreciably high bulk density of 3.945 g/cm³ is achieved with just 1.0% dopant loading at 1550 °C accounting for achievement of 99.62% of the theoretical density value for pure alpha-alumina while the dopant-less alumina compact has attained only 95.45% under the identical condition. It implies that reactive Cr₂O₃ precursor derived from Cr(OH)₃ gel has marked doping action on alpha-alumina sintering by drastic reduction of apparent porosity with marked enhancement of bulk density at 1550 °C. A little fall in density has been observed with 1.5% of Cr₂O₃ precursor probably due to more grain growth and presence of more closed as well as open pores in the fired body.

Mechanical strength is of great importance while considering alumina ceramic for structural application. The

Fig. 5 indicates a tremendous improvement of compressive strength for Cr₂O₃ precursor based alumina compacts over that of dopant-free compacts. Irrespective of dopant content up to 1.0%, a remarkably high compressive strength of over 10950 kg/cm² is achieved at 1550 °C followed by a slight fall at 1.5% of dopant content. The descending trend of compressive strength may be caused by the presence of more porosity and generation of strains in alumina lattice from enhanced solid solubility of Cr³⁺ ions with α -Al₂O₃.

Thus, achievement of appreciably high mechanical strength, high bulk density and negligible apparent porosity exhibited by the α -Al₂O₃ compacts in presence of 1.0% Cr₂O₃ precursor during firing at 1550 °C is attributed to the removal of open porosity as well as controlled crystal growth, ordered distribution and better interlocking of the crystalline phase.

Thermal shock resistance of all Cr₂O₃ doped α -Al₂O₃ compacts fired at 1550 °C was determined at 1000 °C by air quenching method which was observed to exceed +25 cycles for all samples while that with dopant free one was just 20 cycles.

Powder XRD patterns (Figs. 6 and 7) of Al₂O₃ compacts sintered with or without Cr₂O₃ dopant at 1550 °C reveal that all the sintered alumina compacts consist of corundum as sole crystalline phase. However, crystallite sizes as well as interplaner spacing of dopant-containing alumina compacts are found to increase a little. Average crystallite size for 1.0% Cr₂O₃ doped sintered alumina has been estimated as 55 nm while that of dopant-free alumina compacts as 50 nm using Debye-Scherrer equation. The interplaner spacing of Cr₂O₃ doped alumina is also changed to 1.62 Å from 1.60 Å for dopant-free compacts. The profound doping action of reactive Cr₂O₃ precursor on α -Al₂O₃ consolidation may be due to isomorphous substitution of aluminium ions and/or filling up of vacant octahedral sites in alumina lattice by isovalent chromium ions.

SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of sintered alumina compacts with or without dopant at 1550 °C are presented in Figs. 8 and 9. Comparison of the microstructures of sintered alumina compacts reveals that reactive Cr₂O₃ precursor favors the formation and homogeneous distribution of sharp polygonal α -Al₂O₃ crystals with controlled grain growth. Chromia forms isomorphous solid solution by either occupying vacant sites or substi-

Fig. 6. XRD pattern of α - Al_2O_3 compacts sintered at 1550 °C without dopant.

Fig. 7. XRD pattern of α - Al_2O_3 compacts sintered at 1550 °C with 1.0% Cr_2O_3 precursor.

Fig. 8. SEM image of fractured surface of α -alumina fired at 1550 °C for two hours without dopant.

Fig. 9. SEM image of fractured surface of α - Al_2O_3 fired at 1550 °C for two hours with 1.0% Cr_2O_3 precursor.

tuting aluminium ions in the octahedral sites of rhombohedral alumina lattice. The Cr ions with larger cationic size than Al ions (ionic size of Al^{3+} 1.07 Å and that of Cr^{3+} 1.28 Å) favor more volume as well as grain boundary diffusion resulting in densification of alumina matrix. This process allows intense densification along with controlled grain growth as enhanced mass transport along the grain boundary brings about rapid removal of vacancies during sintering process. Thus dopant ions function as a grain growth accelerator in alumina sintering. With minor addition of Cr_2O_3 in pure alumina compacts, the open porosity less than 0.3% in fired sample is observed to accumulate at the grain boundaries. But the observed

microstructure is somewhat different in dopant-free sample. The existence of a few propagated fractures and microcracks along grain boundary of coarser faceted alumina grains with occasional open and sealed voids surrounded by clusters of elongated corundum grains are noticed in dopant-free alumina sample. But the minute presence of reactive Cr_2O_3 precursor leads to the development of the dense, medium sized and uniformly distributed sharp polygonal α - Al_2O_3 grains during sintering of pure alumina at 1550 °C through the isomorphous solid solution of chromia dopant with Al_2O_3 matrix. SEM micrographs reveal narrow grain size range from 2.5 to 3.0 μm while virgin α - Al_2O_3 compacts show such range from 1.5–3.0 μm depicting moderate degree of grain growth in dopant-added alumina bodies during sintering at 1550 °C.

The sintering action of minor chromia on α - Al_2O_3 system may be explained in the way that chromium ions of Cr_2O_3 precursor can readily substitute isostructural, isovalent aluminium ions in α - Al_2O_3 lattice. In the process, it forms complete solid solution with consequent generation of significant directional strain in hexagonal alumina lattice due to their ionic size variation that helps in sintering process of α - Al_2O_3 system.

Conclusion :

From the above sintering study of pure α - Al_2O_3 compacts in presence of *in situ* formed Cr_2O_3 precursor, the following conclusions may be drawn :

(i) The minor loading of *in situ* formed Cr_2O_3 precursor markedly enhances the densification process at a relatively low temperature in pure α - Al_2O_3 compacts.

(ii) The optimal addition of 1.0% (w/w) Cr_2O_3 precursor leads to exhibit remarkable improvement in thermomechanical properties of α - Al_2O_3 compacts at 1550 °C.

(iii) No chromium bearing phase has been detected from XRD pattern of dopant added sintered compacts, indicating complete solid solubility of chromia in alumina matrices thereby minimizing the chances of hazards from free chromium ions.

(iv) SEM image confirms the beneficial action of *in situ* Cr_2O_3 precursor in the pure α - Al_2O_3 consolidation process as a controlled grain growth accelerator. Dense coherent α - Al_2O_3 compacts with substantial thermomechanical strength and uniform medium grained microstructure has been developed at 1550 °C.

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